

The meaning of
sustainable living
communities:
connectedness,
responsibility and
independence

MASTER THESIS

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Wageningen University,

Forest and Nature Conservation

2025

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January 9, 2026

Preface

Dear reader,

This report presents my academic thesis for the masters' study Forest and Nature conservation at the Wageningen University, Netherlands. A strong personal interest is reflected in this research: in times of national and global unrest, and biodiversity and climate crises, what drives humans who dare to deviate from the beaten path and take their own route, and why?

With this research I dove into a small aspect of this question. The thesis laying in front of you, is about the meaning the founders and residents of ecovillages attain to them. For this reason, I approached residents and/or founders of Dutch ecovillages to capture and document their experiences regarding this topic. It was an honour to be trusted with the oftentimes inspiring, personal, and moving stories that emerged during the interviews and conversations I had with the participants.

Therefore I would like to firstly express my honest and sincere gratitude towards the residents and founders who participated in this research. Being welcomed in your homes and visiting your thoughtfully developed dwellings was truly an inspiring experience. Secondly, my thesis supervisor Roel During has my sincere gratitude. As discussion partner, writing help, and mentor, he played an indispensable role in the process of carrying out and writing this research. Even so, I'd like to express my sincere thanks to Jim van Laar for the more technical guidance provided from the chair group Forest- and nature conservation policy at Wageningen University. Finally I want to thank my beloved family and friends for their unconditional support in the – sometimes demanding – times of researching and writing.

This report does not only bring this research to conclusion, it is also marks the end of my study years and the beginnings of new opportunities.

Enjoy reading.

~ Eva

Abstract

Recent years have seen an increase in the number of ecovillages in the Netherlands. Between and within these ecovillages much diversity in for example worldviews, scale, and organisational design is to be found. However, from academic niches and mainstream media platforms, information around ecovillages is centred mostly around the sustainability aspects of ecovillages. However, besides a way to live sustainably, the meaning of the ecovillage for their residents and the reasons why people want to set up an ecovillage seem to differ, but this has not been given much attention by academics or media platforms.

The importance of a deeper understanding of the diversity in ecovillages is relevant on several levels. Firstly, on a personal level as it sheds light on the diversity of meaning for people that can be attained to ecovillages. Secondly, for policy it is important to understand the increase in ecovillages better, as it is a phenomenon that becomes increasingly popular. Therefore, the aim of this research is to explore the meaning of ecovillages for their founders and residents. These meanings arise from personal views, life histories and social interaction. This process is seen through the lens of social constructivism and captured in personal life stories. Therefore, interviews will be conducted in the form of biographies. These biographies reveal how people understand the construction of their meaning for ecovillages throughout time.

The results suggest that the 'regular' living environment of the founders and residents is insufficiently connected with their values, ideals, and needs. This led to frustrations among the residents and developers and made their 'regular' living place often feel unsatisfying to them. Overall, the ecovillage residents and founders experienced the ecovillage as better aligning with their needs, ideals and values. However, simultaneously certain aspect of living in an ecovillage can be experienced as challenging.

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1. Introduction

Ecovillages in the Netherlands are booming. Only in three years' time - from 2021 to 2023 - 13 new ecovillage projects applied at Global Ecovillage Network Netherlands (Global Ecovillage Network Nederland; 2021, 2022, 2023). In 2023 the Netherlands counted 56 ecovillage initiatives, of which some are still in their realisation phase.

The Global Ecovillage Network (GEN), the overarching organisation that educates about ecovillages, lobbies for them, and brings ecovillages together globally, tried to capture its definition even though there is much variety within ecovillages (Joubert, 2017). She describes ecovillages as: *“An ecovillage is an intentional, traditional or urban community that is consciously designed through locally owned, participatory processes in all four dimensions of sustainability (social, culture, ecology and economy) to regenerate their social and natural environments”*.

The variety in ecovillages is reflected by the various narratives and objectives within ecovillages if one looks at the origins of individual ecovillages. For example, Findhorn in Scotland, also known as 'the mother of ecovillages', has its origins in being a spiritual community (Findhorn Foundation, n.d.). The idea for ecovillage Boekel started with the realization of Ad Vlems, one of the founders, that he wanted his child to be able to see a positive future ahead of him (Ecodorp Boekel, 2020). Community living project PPauw in Wageningen had its origins in the squatting of a piece of land and calls itself also a creative and ecological fringe (ten Hoedt & van Barneveld, 2014). These are all differently rooted initiatives called ecovillages, but they were all set up with different intentions. An ecovillage can thus be seen as an umbrella term for the diversity of communities, each with its own narrative about their existence and their destination.

1.1. What has been written about ecovillages?

The rise in popularity of ecovillages can also be observed in what has been reported about them. However, even though there is much diversity between and within the ecovillages, the increased interest in ecovillages from outside centres itself around the sustainability aspect. Whether in popular media or academics, often the ecovillages are being described within this narrow scope of climate change and the unsustainable way we humans relate to nature.

1.1.1. Academics about ecovillages

Mostly the objective of academic research is to describe ecovillages as phenomena with a potential to be a model for sustainability that has a possible influence outside of the borders of the initiative itself and thus contributing to transformative change (Kunze & Avelino, 2009, 2015; Dias et al., 2017). Or the research around ecovillages is about how they can be optimised concerning their sustainability goals and how this sustainability aspect can be

scaled up (Daly, 2017; Barani et al., 2018; Juskaite, 2019). What can be observed is that the research stays within the common denominator of ecovillages, which is sustainability. The research itself is often not about the diversity of worldviews, meanings, and values but gets straight into the sustainability aspect of the ecovillages. Not to be mistaken, within the interest of academic research around ecovillages the diversity within them is mostly acknowledged. However, often it does not go further than mentioning the diversity-aspect in the introduction, so it does not necessarily get into depth to what this diversity means.

To get a bit more into depth: the research of Avelino & Kunze (2009, 2015) is about ecovillages and how they can contribute to sustainability transitions; the potential of ecovillages to contribute to transformative change. What is being meant with transformative change is rather than optimising the current system and staying within the status quo, a radical new system and ways of doing is brought into life, parallel to the existing one: the status quo (Haxeltine et al., 2016). This parallel system challenges the status quo and can bring about structural, in this case sustainable changes to the societal system. Following Avelino and Kunze (2009, 2015), the ecovillage movement could have a potential for sustainability transitions: how and in what way ecovillages influence the 'mainstream'. They explored the transition potential of ecovillages. They emphasise how the communal aspect of ecovillages makes them unique.

The research by Dias et al. (2017) identifies a problem in the capitalistic approach to sustainability. They argue that there's another more holistic way of thinking needed to move forward towards a sustainable future. The research is positioned in the context where capitalism is perceived as contributing to planetary degradation and unsustainability, through the appropriation of the concept of sustainability by capitalistic models. Ecovillages are framed as places that challenge these unsustainable capitalistic models. This paper of Dias et al. (2017) aligns with the research of Kunze and Avelino (2009, 2015) as both studies suggest the need for a different discourse towards sustainability outside of the status quo. They both focus on ecovillages as societal alternatives, highlighting them as holistic systems to address sustainability issues.

1.1.2. Mainstream media about ecovillages

While academic niches show interest in ecovillages by recognising their potential for contributing to sustainable societies, the mainstream media often does not share this perspective. Most of the Dutch media articles about ecovillages are in local newspapers, if a new ecovillage initiative arises in the area they operate in (De Boer, 2023; Mascini, 2024). Often there's writing about what the residents are planning to do in their ecovillage. It gets stuck in questions about how the organisers are planning to build, where it will be built, how many people will live there and that it will be a sustainable place where people share facilities. Also, a glimpse of disinterest or shallow reporting can often be perceived. In an article about the ecovillage Land van Aine the reporter wrote down that the new, small,

two-room house looks tidy and doesn't have a tv (Looden, 2023). Things that are not specific for ecovillages.

A lack of understanding can be recognised in reportings about ecovillages, as the articles often remain at surface level and describe tangible aspects of the ecovillage. If they would have more in-depth interest then interviews would get more into the worldviews, meaning, and values behind the creation or choice to live in an ecovillage. The potential which academics see in ecovillages is usually not recognised and reproduced in mainstream media.

1.1.3. Academic and media articles

Both ways, the main focus is on the environmental sustainability aspect of ecovillages. Academic and mainstream media mostly focus on the obvious common denominator across all ecovillages which is the sustainability aspect and don't get into depth on what the diversity means. In the sense that there are more aspects to ecovillages that are important for the people living there.

1.2. The meaning of ecovillages

If one would look closer at the ways ecovillages came about, one would see that it comes from different ideologies, different standpoints. One would think there may be many different meanings associated to an ecovillage by their residents. Besides a way to live sustainable, the approach to what an ecovillage means for their residents and the reasons why people want to set up an ecovillage seem to differ. Moreover, sustainability is also not a defined concept. Its definition may differ across ecovillages.

The importance of a deeper understanding of the diversity in ecovillages is relevant on several levels. Firstly, on a personal level as it sheds light on the diversity of meaning for people that can be attained to ecovillages. Secondly, for policy it is important to understand the increase in ecovillages better, as it is a phenomenon that becomes increasingly popular. Policymaking related to ecovillages or different ways of organizing a living may get more important as more ecovillage initiatives or alike might be popping up in the future. Being better informed about the diversity of meanings attained to ecovillages, helps to understand this movement better and helps informing policies based upon current empirical insights.

The aim of this research was to explore the meaning of ecovillages for their founders and residents. These meanings arise from personal views, life histories and social interaction. To reach this goal the following questions have been answered:

Main research question:

What meaning do the ecovillage residents and founders attribute to their ecovillage?

Sub-research questions:

Why do ecovillage residents and founders choose to live in an ecovillage?

How is the ecovillage lifestyle experienced by their residents and founders?

2. Theoretical framework

This chapter presents the theoretical framework by discussing scientific theories relevant for this research.

2.1. Social constructivism

In this research, the establishment-process of ecovillages is seen through the lens of social constructivism. Social constructivism is a theory – often classified under relativist theories – about how knowledge is constructed and how people learn (Adams, 2006). In social constructivism, learning happens through interaction with other actors (Ruijters, 2006; Jafari Amineh & Davatgari Asl, 2015). People come to a new understanding, integrating prior knowledge and experiences with newly acquired knowledge (Ruijters & Simons, 2012). Subsequently new outcomes follow this process of meaning making. This newly acquired knowledge may also interact with their belief and value systems leading to different ways of doing, changing identities or worldviews being adapted (Illeris, 2009).

This learning process relates to the meaning being given to ecovillages as it shapes the understanding of ecovillages and has influences the meaning people attain to them. Their ways of learning about ecovillages determined the value ascribed to it and what feeling they have for this matter. For example, if they would walk past an old oak in the city park where they used to walk past every week with your lately deceased grandma, this tree would have a different meaning to them than the person that walks past the tree in their lunch break every day. The ways they came to know that tree and knowledge around it – the place where they walked with their grandma or where they had shade from their lunch break – determines the meaning the tree has for one.

However, from the social constructivist viewpoint, learning happens in interaction with other actors and thus it is not loose standing from its environment (Ruijters, 2006; Jafari Amineh & Davatgari Asl, 2015; Hein, 1999). Therefore, the meaning people attain to the establishment of and living in ecovillages relates to the learning process that came before in relation to their environment. It is still ongoing while people create ecovillages and live in them as they're still interacting with their environment. The way people construct(ed) knowledge is essential in understanding why people attribute a certain meaning to things. This can also be applied to this research on the meaning of ecovillages by their founders and residents.

Therefore, to discover what meaning the ecovillage residents and founders attribute to their ecovillage, it is important to examine their motivation for choosing to live in the ecovillage and their lived experience of the ecovillage lifestyle. By analysing how residents and founders explain the meaning of the ecovillage in relation to life-events, personal histories, and drivers, this research aims to understand what the ecovillage represents in their life.

This will give a better understanding how the meaning for ecovillages came about, this can be called meaning-making process.

2.1.1. Biographies

This meaning-making process described above can be captured in personal life stories. The personal life stories emerge from an endless amount of experiences being shared with each other, being responded to, and being woven together and connected with other experiences. The personal life stories are thus a web of constructed narratives that can be called biographies. Biographies can tell how someone experiences certain events, how they view those experiences, which ways they connect life events, and how they construct meaning from them. For this research the biographies form the basis to explore narratives and discourses in the personal life stories (Taylor & Littleton, 2006). This biographical method can be used to find out how the residents of ecovillages' meaning came about. It is based on personal experience, how people themselves tell stories about how their meaning is constructed. In the case of this research, narratives around why the residents of ecovillages chose to establish and live in them and what the ecovillage lifestyle means for its residents, can tell something about the knowledge construction which shaped their meaning for ecovillages.

In these biographies can be deciphered how people understand the construction of their meaning for ecovillages throughout time. Analysing biographies is a suitable methodology, as it takes into account that a narrative is in the first place situated in the here and now, but also that it makes sense of past events. As it is said by Taylor & Littleton (2006): *"We understand this biography as a situated construction, produced for and constituted within each new occasion of talk but shaped by previously presented versions and also by understandings which prevail in the wider discursive environment, such as expectations about the appropriate trajectory of a life."* Biographies are thus an ongoing process, which is constructed in the now, but in interaction with the past and present.

Biographies are a narrative-discursive approach. Which means a discourse can be found in a narrated story. A biographical narrative is being told about what ecovillages mean to its residents. As these will be biographical stories, people make sense about their life in constructing these stories. In these stories the context of the meaning-making process is given. What stories have the residents of ecovillages made in how they relate to it. These stories may reveal what meaning there is behind the choices of living in a ecovillage. This narrative-discursive approach of biographies can be helpful in finding out within the narratives people tell what discourses are in life trajectories and meanings around ecovillages (Taylor & Littleton, 2006).

3. Methodology

This methodological chapter provides insight into the composition of the dataset, the interview method used, how the data were analysed, the co-creation with participants, the researchers' positionality, and the ethical considerations of the study.

3.1. Dataset

3.1.1. Participant selection

The research activities contained 9 interviews with Dutch speaking residents or initiators of 5 different ecovillages in the Netherlands. The ecovillages varied from yet to be built to a maximum of 10 years after completion.

The ecovillages

The interview candidates were part of one of these five ecovillages

- Land van Aine in Ter Apel
- De Beuk in Wageningen (in the realisation phase)
- Arneco in Arnhem
- De Kleverbergh in Erlecom
- Iewan in Nijmegen-Lent

The interview candidates

(the names of the interview candidates are fictionalised)

- Suus
- Babette
- Jasmine
- Bram
- Petra
- Victor
- Rose
- Michaela
- Fons

3.2. Interview method

A qualitative research approach has been chosen as we delved into personal life narratives about meanings for ecovillages. A qualitative method was the most suitable approach as this captured the subjectivity of the meaning founders and residents had for their ecovillage and the lifestyle associated with it. The interviews were recorded and transcribed using Microsoft Teams or Microsoft Word.

The interview candidates' personal life narratives have been captured through narrative interviews and, more specifically, biographical interviewing. In the narrative interview method, the interviewer invited the interviewee to tell stories which were in this case, personal life narratives relevant to the research subject, by asking for a life story around that subject, for example (Kvale, 2007). The main role for the interviewer was to be the listener to the story, they could ask questions for clarification or guide the interviewee to continue the story. However, the starting point was for the interviewee to tell their story.

Even though the interviewer positioned themselves as a listener in the narrative interview approach, knowledge was produced in interview interaction (Kvale, 2007). The interview was seen as a way of knowledge construction between interviewer and interviewee, as the interviewees were asked by the interviewer to tell their own story about their lived experiences. The way of asking by the interviewer, body language such as nodding, and silences or reassuring noises like 'uhuh' all influenced the construction of the story by the interviewee. Therefore, the personal life narratives captured by the biographical interview were narratives co-constructed by both the interviewee and the interviewer. Therefore, it was also important to consider the interviewer's positionality, on which more elaboration can be found in paragraph 3.4.

3.3. Data analysis

3.3.1. Interview interpretation

The first interpretation of the interview by the researcher has been given back to the interviewee in question to check if it fits the interviewees' perception of what narrative they have told in the interview. In this way the personal life narrative is kept close to how the interviewee himself told the story.

3.3.2. Descriptive analysis

To analyse the interpretations of the interview the method of theoretical reading has been used (Kvale 2007). This approach does not rely on a systemic coding process. It rather involves repeated immersion in the data through a re-reading process for understanding and interpreting narratives deeply. At first, the interviews were read fully to gain an overall impression of the text. During second reading, emergent passages related to meaning-making, motivations and experiences were highlighted and distinguished from one-another. The researcher then revisited the emergent passages and identified which themes appeared across multiple interviews and which stood more independently. Subsequently, interpretive writing and reflective rumination on the interviews led to a layered perspective on the emergent themes in the interviews. With this process of repeated reading and immersion in the data familiarity with the material is developed. This allowed meanings in the textual material, consisting of personal life narratives, to emerge. This process enabled the

researcher to get thoroughly familiar with the data, which allowed patterns to emerge naturally.

These findings have been reported in a continuous interpretive text, in which the researcher takes the reader with them in their reasoning around the narratives the interviewees have told, how the researcher understands the narratives and which patterns it sees. Quotes from the narratives are given for clarity and for the readers own interpretation. These interview passages may speak for themselves rather than the text interpreting it firstly.

Because the analysis is grounded in personal life narratives, the focus lies on life events as coherent units rather than on isolated words or sentences, as is common in textual analysis. Life events offer a more meaningful lens for understanding the motivations and meanings that residents attribute to founding and inhabiting ecovillages. By foregrounding events instead of short textual fragments, the analysis aligns more closely with the research aim.

As the interviews have been given in Dutch, language tools such as Google Translate and AI language tools Microsoft CoPilot and ChatGPT (GPT-5) have been used for simple translational features, at moments where the language knowledge of the researcher fell short.

3.3.3. Identified themes prior to the interviews

To ensure that the main and sub-research questions were effectively addressed, prior to the interviews a small number of themes was prepared. This provided structure to the interviews and guaranteed that central research themes were addressed. The identified themes were:

- motivation to join or set up the ecovillage
- experience of setting up and/or living in the ecovillage
- trajectory towards setting up and/or living in the ecovillage

Elaboration on the themes can be found in the topic list (Appendix II).

3.4. Co-creation and positionality

As the residents are not independent from their environment, also this thesis is not independent from its context. Recognizing that the researcher who interviewed the residents of ecovillages co-created the story as they may have responded differently from one interviewer to another, everyone may have asked questions differently for example, the body language differed from person to person, gender may have influenced what answers were given (Ongena, 2005). Also, each interviewer had a different background which also influenced how the narratives of the interviewees were understood. It is not fully comprehensible how it exactly influenced each other, but one thing that can be done is to

make a profile sketch of the first researcher who conducted the interviews and interpreted the narratives.

3.4.1. Profile sketch

Even though effort had been made to keep the researchers' position as neutral as possible in the research, the researcher could not go around her positionality and the influence it inevitably had on this research. The background and interests of the researcher influenced the research as her interests and viewpoints co-determined which questions she asked in the interviews and which she did not, which red threads she found in the stories the ecovillage founders and residents told and which not, which literature she found relevant to mention and which not. She was aware of her positionality, she saw it as something not loose standing from the research. She wanted to take the viewpoint for this research that the interviews and the final report have been co-created between her and the interviewees. Therefore, a conversational atmosphere was created by having a small introductory exchange at the beginning of the interview. This offered an opening for both participant and interviewer to share who they are and where each came from, creating openness and familiarity with each other's background. Next to that, the researcher has given the interpretations of the interviews back to the interviewees to check for righteousness of the interpretations

A short profile sketch for the reader of this thesis, of the researcher Eva Kuipers: She is, in times of conducting and finishing this research for her master's studies Forest and Nature conservation at the Wageningen University, a mid-20'ies female from the Netherlands. She grew up in a family of which both parents have studied on an academic level in the environmental and agricultural domain. She considers herself political left and progressive. She has a personal as well as professional interest in ecological and sustainable living, and how we as humans relate to life, nature, and each other.

3.5. Ethical considerations

Interviewing about personal life stories is a delicate matter. As the term itself suggests, it is a personal story which in the end will be published in the public domain. It is ensured that the interviews won't be published with personal details and the storage of interviews and contacts are confidential. Integrity guidelines of the Wageningen University have been followed, which means that the Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (KNAW et al., 2018) has been followed. Prior informed consent is obtained from the interviewees before conducting the interviews, and they have been asked to complete the consent form found in Annex I.

Things to consider as interviewer before undertaking the interviews is that there may have been power asymmetry, as the interviewer was there from a professional point of view,

asking questions. The interviewer wanted to know something of the interviewee (Kvale 2007). The interview was not a conversation with a goal in itself, it has instrumental means. It has been interpreted with a certain view. In first instance the interviewer had a monopoly of itself in interpreting the answers. However, as mentioned before in paragraph 2.4, in this study the researcher has given the interpretation back to the interviewee to check for righteousness of the interpretations.

4. Results

The first part of this chapter addresses the motivation of the founders and residents to live in the ecovillage. The second part focuses on the lived experiences of inhabiting and establishment of the ecovillage. This results section is structured narratively, in line with the biographical style of this research.

4.1. Motivations to live in the ecovillage

4.1.1. The need for contact

For four of the interviewees, the search for an ecovillage started with the search for community and a social life, in which they felt more emotional connectedness. For many, the lives they previously lived felt too socially fragmented or isolated. They felt a lack of connectedness and community and expressed a desire to cultivate relationships in a more organic way.

Even though many had social contacts outside of their household, they grew tired of the conventional way of interacting with friends or neighbours. Needing to schedule an evening to meet each other, or the lack of reciprocity when asking a neighbour for a favour was not how they envisioned and wanted to organise their lives. Continuing for another twenty years on the same path is not what they envisioned for themselves. In contrast to the structured nature of interactions with neighbours or friends, there were also more natural forms of contact with which they felt much more comfortable.

For example, Suus was involved in a gardening group which she could join and withdraw from whenever she wanted. This felt less forced and more natural to her. She appreciated the flexibility of the gardening group, without fixed agreements and expectations. That was the kind of contact she was looking for. The togetherness evolved rather than it being predetermined. This contrasted with the structured meetings with her friends, which she grew tired of. In the gardening group, she could better regulate her level of involvement, she felt more autonomy.

Suus: "What I was mainly looking for was meaning. I had kind of like: I actually wanted to live in a co-housing group. Meanwhile I started meditating and had been gardening with a group for a long time already, went on group vacations often. So I thought: I want to be part of a group so I can join in and step back whenever I want."

Rose mentions that she feels drawn to more communal living, embracing a more sustainable lifestyle, and living smaller. This is a common thread throughout her life. As a child she was used to share and live together as she grew up in a large family. Therefore, it was normal for her to help others and to welcome visitors to join in for a meal. In addition, she has lived in many housing groups and during the time she lived in Africa the local expat community she was part of, was also dependent on each other. Therefore, opening up her home is very enjoyable and important for her. However, she notices in the average Dutch neighbourhood this is more difficult.

Rose: "I oftentimes give the example of my terribly nice neighbour. Yeah I'm just someone who forgets to buy potatoes and then ask: 'do you have a potato?'. And I can ask that three times but he never asks anything in return. And it doesn't need to be a potato, but..."

She says reciprocity is necessary to do something for each other. If that is missing, the contact becomes too one-sided, as such with her neighbour. This ultimately leads her to stop asking for that favour. She finds it important that both parties experience it as a balance.

Rose: "And I don't want to be that annoying neighbour who is always coming to borrow potatoes because she doesn't have her life together."

For Babette the social aspect is also an important driving force behind her motivation to establish and live in the ecovillage. She mentions she has somewhat the tendency to withdraw and be on herself. However, she notices that leading a withdrawn life does not do her good and therefore she has committed herself to seek more contact with others. Babette observes that people lead a more fragmented life and fears that this poses a threat to peace on earth. This is also a motivation for her to seek more contact with others as she notices this contact and connection is an essential thing where people are moving away from.

All three women express a desire for more open, relaxed, and effortless contact on a daily basis. Their lives do not naturally overlap with those of others. In their experience they were living an individualised and self-contained life. Their daily life was lived separately from others instead of being shared. Instead, they had a desire for contact that naturally emerged, instead of it being planned or arranged.

While, living communally, Petra and Michaela discovered they enjoyed this communal way of living. Prior to establishing the ecovillage, Petra lived in another communal living environment, in which she ended up by coincidence. At first she was looking for a place where she could live on her own, as she thought that that would suit her better. However,

after a tip she visited the living group and was pleasantly surprised. She valued the shared responsibility, large vegetable garden, nature area, and taking decisions together.

Petra: "Instead of living a bit more independently, I actually started living much more together."

Eating together, sharing the household, doing chores. She found it a very pleasant way of life. She discovered something deeply meaningful for her, without specifically seeking for it. It fitted her, it felt like family, even though the communal aspect didn't necessarily appeal to her in the first place.

Petra: "What I thought after was like, oh, that something I want to keep doing if I ever leave here."

Also, for Michaela it wasn't her original plan to establish a shared living project. However, it proved to be a way to realise her dreams more easily. Although she was not initially looking for it, Michaela was later surprised by how fulfilling it felt to live more communally in the ecovillage.

4.1.2. Self-sufficiency

For two interviewees – Fons and Bram – self-sufficiency is an important motivation for wanting to live differently. In their 'regular' city houses they experienced insufficient space and freedom to shape their lives in a more self-sufficient way. Although this did not necessarily mean that they wanted to live in an ecovillage, they did have the desire for space to live self-sufficient.

Both felt unable to create the lifestyle that is meaningful to them in their 'regular' city houses. The meaningful aspects of self-sufficient living differ between both. For Bram autonomy in food provisioning is very important, while for Fons self-sufficiency is more centred around the communal aspect of food provisioning.

Bram clearly tried to adapt his terraced house to his own preferences. He made his home greener and greener, up to a point where he even started planting fruit trees in the whole neighbourhood. Eventually he reached a point where he felt it was getting out of hand and he realised that in their 'regular' city house it felt impossible to reach true self-sufficiency.

For Fons the meaningful aspects of his life in the city differed from the meaningful aspects he experiences in his ecovillage. In the city his work, relationship, and personal development were the main factors that provided significance in his life. However, at a certain point this wasn't fulfilling for him anymore. He wanted to live more in accordance with his values and felt restricted in the city. Connection with nature and spending time on pursuits other than earning money were essential aspects of this. In both of the aspects he felt restricted in his former city house.

As both felt limited in living according to their values in their 'regular' city homes, they began searching for a different type of dwelling. Neither had initially envisioned living in an ecovillage, this developed naturally. In first instance, either of them explored to buy a farm independently or with a small group of people. However, they found out this was financially unfeasible. As a result, they looked for a larger group with whom they could establish or join a bigger, collective, and sustainable housing project.

4.1.3. Sustainability and living healthy through connectedness with nature

Sustainability and care for nature

Three interviewees – Jasmine, Bram, and Fons – mentioned that they experienced a lack of connectedness in their 'regular' city houses. They hold a critical stance towards society and observe that their sense of disconnection stems from the fragmented and individualised character of modern society, as they perceive it. Whereas earlier, interviewees primarily missed social connectedness, for Bram, Jasmine, and Fons the lack of connectedness concerned a broader, more integral sense: the feeling that their surroundings, their lives, and nature are interconnected. In the city they did not feel connected to their place and surroundings, and to the feeling of unity that comes with it.

This lack of connectedness with place was therefore not only social or emotional in nature, but also touched upon the values concerning how they wish to lead their lives. In the city they scarcely experienced that sense of coherence. According to them, connectedness with nature and ecological action are closely intertwined, as those who do not feel connected to a place also find it difficult to take care of it. In their regard, this is a societal problem as well. They observe that in a culture that detaches people from their environment, it becomes more difficult for individuals to act in an ecologically responsible manner.

This vision is strongly reflected in their concerns about the state of the world in terms of nature and the environment. They feel a drive not to harm nature and the world but rather make a positive contribution. They feel responsible towards future generations to leave the planet in a better condition than before and not to pass the problems onto the next generation.

Victor explicitly emphasises that he has experienced how a lack of connectedness with nature leads to less empathetic behaviour. In addition he links connection with nature to personal health benefits. For him, it is not only about planetary health, but also about how people feel, function, and interact with each other in society.

City life and connectedness with nature

Despite their awareness of the harm their practices caused to the environment, Victor and Fons mentioned they found it difficult to sustain an environmental friendly lifestyle in the

city. Whereas in the ecovillage this was much easier. They reasoned that in the city it was much harder to notice the consequences of their polluting habits. Although they intended to live sustainably, the absence of nature left them disconnected and diminished their sense of urgency.

As they felt less confronted with their own polluting practices due to their disconnection from nature, urban everyday life felt easier and less demanding. They did not feel the urgency to take other organisms into account that were harmed by their behaviour. However, simultaneously it also created an inner contradiction. They were aware of their polluting practices but did not experience their consequences. Therefore they could continue more easily on the same path.

In the city their lives felt more self-centred. At times it felt as if they were the only beings of significance. Yet that was not how they knew life to be. In their city homes, they did not feel confronted with their destructive habits. Victor remarks that, for him, life in a city-centre apartment feels too clinical and clean being cut off from nature.

The reduced connection with nature hinders a sustainable and ecologically way of living, they believe. In the city, for example, they did not feel connectedness with nature and other beings, despite their knowledge about the interconnectedness of the ecological system. Based upon their own experience, the problem they see in this disconnection from nature is the lack of responsibility for their surroundings, as they didn't see the consequences of their actions. This contrasts with their ecovillage experience, where they lived immersed in nature.

Victor: [about life in the ecovillage] "Wasps and flies and woodlice and plants sneaking through your window or things like that, or when you leave your door open too long and the chicken comes inside. Nature comes inside just like you go outside. Yeah, at all times you're aware that you're not the only one here."

The presence of nature around them brought more awareness of the life surrounding them, making it much harder to ignore their harmful practices. Living in their ecovillage which is closely intertwined with nature, enables this form of connection. Therefore, they see the importance of directly integrating nature into one's life, as a daily reminder that they are not the only beings on this planet that matter. This is a key aspect of their ecovillages.

Victor: "So you can also just think: it's not there, or that's their problem, or I'll just live in my own house in my own bubble, and let the rest sort it out themselves."

This led them to seek a life more connected with nature. They are convinced that living in nature makes both people and the world healthier. In the ecovillage, they sought greater connectedness, so that they were 'forced' to live more ecologically.

Spirituality and connectedness with nature

Several of the founders and residents mentioned that, for them, connection with nature is closely linked to personal health. For them, nature is integrally connected to health. However, they also referred to different themes that they associate with health: having a clear mind, spirituality, kindness towards others and oneself, and calmness.

For Jasmine in particular, but to a lesser extent also Fons and Victor, connection with the land they live on also has a spiritual aspect. They feel spiritually healthier when they are connected to nature, which for them is equivalent to living in a vital place that contributes to life.

Fons is professionally and personally engaged in anthroposophy, he mentions it has increased his spiritual development. He always found it difficult to connect with a place, whereas in anthroposophical thought, spirituality can be experienced in the earthly realm as he explains. During his travels, he felt as if he couldn't fully connect with places, which felt unsatisfying at times.

Fons: "And then, during my travels, of course I moved around a lot [...] And then, I actually missed connecting on a level deeper. So at some point I thought: Okay, travelling is great, but I've had enough experiences and wish to really connect with one place. And that's ... that concept started to develop and eventually became this [...] Your original question was like: what inspired me? But the anthroposophy actually kind of got the ball rolling to... so that eventually I was able to connect with this place, on this scale."

4.2. The lived experience of living in and establishing the ecovillage

4.2.1. Challenges concerning work and social pressure

A recurring theme among the interviewees is the social pressure and workload that comes with living in and establishing the ecovillage. Some founders and residents experience challenges related to workload, social demands, and task-related discussions. Friction can arise when different perspectives on tasks are not adequately addressed.

One of the interviewees - Suus – mentions a list of the many responsibilities she takes on. As the initiative grew over time, the workload of those tasks also increased. As a result, she was forced to let go of some of her responsibilities.

Suus: "I'm the coordinator of the vegetable garden, and of the PR, and of the volunteer and of the workshops. Before I was handling the practical facilities too but it all became a bit too much since we're growing quite rapidly. Yeah and all the tasks just keep growing too."

Some founders and residents indicate that the frequency of social interactions in their ecovillage sometimes feels overwhelming or too demanding and express a need for a bit more peace and quiet in their own surroundings.

In Suus' ecovillage, a shared dinner is organised several times a week, where everyone can join in. She explains that she joins in 'only' once or twice a week, as she often finds it overwhelming. This suggests that she feels as if she is ought to join dinner more frequently. However, during the current development phase of her ecovillage, she oftentimes feels the need to withdraw. She says she has a stronger need for peace and serenity.

Babette also points out that due to the heavy workload and busy children, it can be difficult to prioritise relaxation and rest. She, however, does feel that within the initiative there is space for everyone's needs. She says that this is also embedded in the ecovillages' culture.

Babette: "Alongside all the 'doing', there is also the pillar of rest, to also give attention to that. That is quite difficult. [...] I do withdraw from it sometimes, when it all becomes a bit too busy and too much for me. Everyone has their own needs in that sense. And that is being seen and acknowledged and appreciated as well."

Some faced other ecovillage related challenges. They got confronted with their own behaviour, which proved less optimal than they had envisioned.

In the ecovillage they experienced what it means to not be able to distance yourself from nature. For some this was very confronting as they had to let go of control. This makes it a challenge to remain connected with nature, other people and the ecovillage, and to keep choosing this way of life, Fons says.

Fons: "It is not always easy. So then... you need to set the intention each time that you truly want it. that you really want to embrace that connection, also... yeah, because you run into difficult things."

4.2.2. Thankfulness for the community

Several founders and residents expressed their gratitude for their current living situation in the ecovillage. For them, the ecovillage fully aligns with their values and wishes. They describe feeling enriched by the experiences and note that everything feels as it should be.

Jasmine shares that everything feels right, now that she lives in her ecovillage. It matches what she was looking for, as it fulfils her desire for an integrated way of living. She longs to integrate the personal, familial, and professional aspects of her life, to have all these aspects in one place. She is deeply grateful for the chance she has gotten to live in her new home.

Jasmine: "Well, I really feel like I'm in the right place now. I am truly... this feels right in every way. Privately, for my personal life, for my family, and also for my professional life. I always find it difficult

to separate those things [...] that's why I became self-employed at some point [...] a kind of urge not to keep those things separate [...] and now it all comes together."

Petra emphasises the mutual support and care that are embedded in the daily life of her ecovillage.

Petra: "Yeah, if someone is ill or has just had a baby, then basically, without anyone asking... Chains are set up to bring food or to help and... do you need anything else?"

Yet, from what she observes in other forms of housing, she realises that this extends ordinary neighbourly relationships. She finds that a pity, as she experiences a great richness in this supportive and shared environment, even though in reality their material wealth is limited.

Petra: "Sometimes people say: 'Oh, I have really nice neighbours, I hardly notice they're there.' And I think, that is almost the best thing you can hope for from your neighbours. And I find that... almost pitiful. When I see how nice it can be to have neighbours I genuinely like. And yeah, who are there for you if needed. [...] So that just feels very rich, while, yeah, we're actually not so wealthy here at all. So that... yeah, that is something I realise quite often."

4.2.3. Sustainability in shared effort

Two founders and/or residents highlight the diversity of skills within the ecovillage and how, through organisation of these skills, it can benefit the community. It uses the already present skills among the residents and whereby the reliance on external expertise is reduced.

Bram explains that within his ecovillage, one resident is skilled in technical matters or bicycle repairs, while others are good at managing social dynamics. Although not all useful professions are represented and not every issue can be solved internally, the diversity in people and skills ensure that many practical tasks within the initiative can be managed. He observes that a range of different skills is needed for the collective to succeed.

Bram: "It's kind of funny, because in the end it's like a miniature city. And actually you need a little bit of everything of course."

He also notices that this is what makes the difference compared to an ordinary street. In the ecovillage, there is the element of collaboration that you do not have in the same way in a regular street.

Bram: "You share that, I think, much more than you would in the average street."

Fons is also very grateful for all these different skills. It makes the ecovillage less dependent on the outside world. This makes the ecovillage more self-sufficient and more affordable. Because there are so many diversely skilled people together, it becomes easier to achieve certain goals within the ecovillage.

Fons: "You also notice that with such a big group you can achieve much more and really realise more self-sufficiency. Because you just have so many different qualities in-house. [...] You don't have to bring in much from outside world, because that becomes too expensive quickly. So here, you can realise that with a much lower budget."

4.2.4. Gained insights

Suus shares that she met her husband on the first day of her search for a different life. She was looking for companionship and quickly found it in the form of her husband. As a result, her needs shifted regarding the ecovillage.

Suus: "So at first it was: as a single person I just want to be part of a group, so I don't need to manage my social life so much. And that's changed now. Now it is more like, yeah, wanting to live more sustainably and having the excitement of helping to set up an ecovillage. Because that is very difficult in the Netherlands."

Now that Bram lives in the ecovillage, he reflects on what has and has not worked. He describes it as his dream project but emphasises that it is not his "final resting place".

Bram: "It's always been a dream-project for me. It still is... I still really like it, but there are parts where I think: well, I don't think this will be my eternal resting place."

He stresses that, despite the great effort he has put into realising his vision, it is important to remain open to the possibility to leave and not to become too attached to the idea that "this is it".

Bram: "You also should avoid the fear of thinking: 'this is it'. because you see that with some people, right? 'I can't sell now because of the bad market' and 'it's always more expensive', that sort of thing. But it is good to keep yourself open, because there's always a way out."

Originally, he envisioned a smaller, more compact community with only a few families living on a farm. However, financially and practically this idea was not feasible. As a result the number of households increased.

Bram: "On average I think that... that we... I actually think it's gotten a bit too big. The number of houses, the number of people... it's just grown a little too big. From a sustainability perspective it's good, but when it comes to self-sufficiency, it becomes more difficult."

These experiences tempered the dreamy side he initially had for the project. Although the realisation of the ecovillage remains an important accomplishment, his original expectations have been adjusted. This illustrates how aspirations and everyday practice can evolve over time within an ecovillage.

5. Discussion

In this discussion, the findings of the study are interpreted. This is being done in relation to the theoretical framework, the research questions and relevant academic literature. As the results chapter mainly described the things that emerged from the interviews, this discussion chapter focuses on explaining the results and to placing them into context. In doing so, the meaning residents attribute to their ecovillage is connected to broader political, sociological, and ecological perspectives. This is achieved through a hybrid description which is analytically grounded while at the same time attentive to the human and narrative character of the data.

5.1. Reasons for living in the ecovillage

From the results it can be deduced that there are two main driving forces mentioned by the residents for choosing to live in an ecovillage. These are easy going contact and ecological awareness. Next to that, the feeling of being constrained within the 'regular' housing system emerges as a common thread running through both themes.

5.1.1. Easy going contact

The results indicate that social reasons are frequently mentioned as motivation for wanting to live differently. Although the interviewees mention various reasons and describe different experiences, their reflections suggest a shared dissatisfaction with the individualised life they experienced. They long for more spontaneous and everyday contact. However, in their previous living situations they often found that such easy going contact was difficult to establish. The founders and/or residents remark that the broader social structure and culture in the Netherlands are not designed for this, it offers too little support for easy going contact and connection between people.

Most founders and/or residents found it difficult to establish this easy going contact within the existing dominant housing and living structure in the Netherlands. As a result, they went looking for alternative forms outside this dominant structure to create a place where such contact could be fostered more easily. This led them to a self-designed ecovillage. In the ecovillage they are developing or have already realised, they explicitly strive to pay attention to this easy-going contact and to create the conditions that facilitate it. Such as shared spaces on the terrain of the ecovillage.

Especially interviewees who have no or no longer children living at home indicated that the need for contact is the main driving force behind setting up the ecovillage. Children often function as a link between adults, since they are taken to sports clubs, parents' evenings that must be attended, or parents meet each other at the schoolyard (Demey et al., 2013; Lachman et al., 2015). Parents encounter one another informally without prior

arrangement, which makes such contacts accessible, easy going, and self-evident. When these routines become obsolete because children move out, or when people have never had children, this kind of spontaneous contact arises much less easily. This can lead to a decrease in social contact, which may increase the risk for loneliness (Kersten et al., 2023). It makes people without children living at home, as well as poorer people, those in poorer health, the elderly, and widowed or single individuals more dependent on their neighbourhood for everyday social contact (Hoogerbrugge & Burger, 2017).

This may be reinforced by broader societal developments. Within Europe, the central position of the nuclear family is declining as it is no longer the only common form of family life (Sobotka & Berghammer, 2021). In addition, more and more Dutch citizens live alone (Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek, 2024). Also, neighbourhoods have a less central role in people's lives, as they have become less relevant due to globalisation and individualisation (Guest & Wierzbicki, 1999; Putnam, 2000). Social networks are increasingly spread across the country and less tied to place. This has resulted in neighbours being less dependent on one another, and social encounters more often take place in a planned rather than spontaneous manner. Although this does not always lead to less social cohesion, it can weaken the sense of community (Völker et al., 2007; Mollenhorst, 2015).

The interviewees do not explicitly describe themselves as being lonely. However, their experiences align with research showing that people who live alone have an increased risk for loneliness or social isolation (Victor et al., 2000). The interviewees' reflections suggest a lack of connection in everyday life and that mainstream Dutch culture does not encourage ordinary daily connection. In the interviewees' ecovillages, explicit attention is given to create spaces to meet each other.

5.1.2. Connection with nature and care for the earth

In addition to the social aspect, ecological awareness and connection with the earth emerged as an important motivation for choosing to live in an ecovillage. Just as the founders/residents felt limited in their ability to foster easy going contact within their 'regular' living environment, they also felt restricted in expanding their ecological practices in that same 'regular' context.

For two of the founders/residents, self-sufficient living is one of the main reasons for wanting to live differently. Even though they both assign a different meaning to self-sufficiency, both interpretations stem from a critical stance toward the global, exhaustion-based food system that prevails over local, sustainable food supplies in the Netherlands. Both felt caught in a system they did not agree with, but in their 'regular' living environment they had limited opportunities to organise their lives differently.

Additionally, three of the founders/residents mentioned that in the city they did not feel connected to nature. Because of this limited sense of connection, their ecological responsibility diminished, causing awareness of the impact of their own actions on nature to fade and become less central in their daily lives. As their ecological responsibility declined, their convictions about caring properly for the earth no longer aligned with the life they were leading in the city, which for them resulted in an inner discrepancy. The absence of integral connectedness in their 'regular' living environment evoked feelings of emptiness and lack of meaning. This was for them the reason to seek another way of living. In this, they wanted both to restore their personal connection with nature, the earth, or the universe, as well as to attempt to organise their lives in a way that does justice to their ecological convictions.

These experiences align with existing literature on nature connectedness in relation to ecological behaviour. Scientists have found that nature connectedness indeed promotes pro-environmental behaviour (Martin et al., 2020). Nature connectedness also has a positive influence on peoples' mental health (Sheffield et al., 2022). At the same time, the degree of nature connectedness is lower in urban areas compared to rural ones (Schönbach et al., 2022). This is in line with the experiences of the interviewees, who felt less connected to nature in the city compared to the ecovillage. Their observation that connectedness with nature fades in the city, making them less inclined to act ecologically, is consistent with the existing literature.

5.2. Transformational change

The findings and motivations of the interviewees who wish to live in an ecovillage go beyond nature connectedness, pro-environmental behaviour, or the need for social contacts. There is a clear common thread running through the themes emerging from the biographies. They all feel trapped in the current system and express the desire to step out of it or to develop an alternative. For them, creating an ecovillage is an opportunity to shape their lives in a way that is more social, sustainable, and connected. Within the existing system, they experience little room to realise these values.

In transition and sustainability research, this tension is often described as the 'dominant regime'. According to transition scholars Loorbach & Oxenaar (2018), this 'regime' refers to thinking within existing systems, aimed at optimising them and preserving shared values and practices. It consists of institutionalised customs, interests, rules, and norms and values that maintain the current system rather than to challenge or break through them.

Several studies have been conducted around ecovillages and their potential for transformational change (Kunze & Avelino, 2009, 2015; Dias et al., 2017). Ecovillages offer the opportunity to experiment with new ways of living and in doing so, to break through the dominant system. The results show that the interviewees not only recognise cognitively that

they are stuck in the dominant regime but also experience this emotionally. Rationally, they acknowledge that their 'regular' living environment offers little opportunity to live according to their ecological and social values. In addition, they feel strong discomfort, alienation, and a decline in meaning when their daily actions do not align with their convictions about caring for the earth.

The above-mentioned experiences show an awareness of the boundaries of the dominant system and the limitations it brings for the interviewees. The establishment of the ecovillage can be seen as a reaction to the dominant regime, to find more personal freedom without the interviewees having a direct political or societal intention with it.

5.3. How the ecovillage is experienced

Setting up an ecovillage requires a high degree of self-organisation because it is largely pioneering work. The organisational structure of the ecovillage necessarily also involves cooperation among the members of the initiative. The residents of the ecovillage have the responsibility for the organisation and functioning of their own living environment and community. This self-organisation is one of the core elements of ecovillages and is often a driving force behind their establishment. In general, in the founding phase of bottom-up initiatives, involvement in social and practical infrastructure is essential for success. The autonomy the ecovillage offers is therefore closely linked to many organisational tasks and intensive collaboration. This also means that social interactions are necessary to keep the initiative running and the boundary between social and professional relations can be blurred. Ecovillage residents need to continuously decide together what kinds of forms of living, housing, and working are meaningful to them. This is a continuous process of meaning-making.

From the results it can be observed that the ecovillage aligns more closely with the needs, ideals, and values of the founders and residents. Living in an ecovillage gives meaning to their lives. With the ecovillage they have constructed a dwelling place and lifestyle that is more in line with their values, ideals, and needs. There seems to be less of a contradiction between what they find valuable in life and how their life looks like in practical terms.

This can be seen in the fact that two residents mention that spirituality is an important part in their lives and also an important part of living in their ecovillage. For both of them, the ecovillage where they now live is a place where they can be more spiritually grounded. The experience that they can connect better with the place where they live, and with the earth. For both it was something they were looking for when they began their search for another way of living and dwelling. Two other residents say that the ecovillage completely aligns with how they want to live and how they had imagined the ecovillage to be. Some enjoy living in the ecovillage so much that they have made it their work to guide or promote communal living.

In addition to the many positive associations, some residents also make critical remarks about their experience with founding and living in their ecovillage. Two residents mention that they also experience certain aspects of life in their ecovillage as confronting. Their motivation to live in an ecovillage stems from the desire to live more ecologically responsible. Precisely because of this, they are confronted more often than before with the consequences of their choice. It forces them to take ecological responsibility where previously they could still escape from it. Because of this, they sometimes experience it as heavy and confronting, despite the fact that they consciously sought and chose for this responsibility.

Many residents also mention the intensity of the communal aspect of the ecovillage. In particular, the work and social pressure is experienced by many as heavy. Several residents also expressed frustrations about the unequal distribution of labour. Expectations towards each other can also cause tensions. For the residents who share many facilities, which makes living together more intensive, the residents placed extra emphasis on personal space, individuality, and autonomy. They seem to have to position themselves more actively in the community than those who had an independent living space alongside shared facilities.

In general, it can be concluded that the communal part of ecovillages is experienced as very valuable, if at the same time a balance is maintained between togetherness and personal space. The importance of a balance in personal space and communality is emphasised in cohousing literature (Heinonen, 2024; Törnqvist, 2020). In these studies, it is mentioned that for the harmonious functioning of the community a balance between privacy and communality is very important. In addition, it is important that the aspect of 'giving and taking' is experienced as reciprocal among the residents.

This is a relevant insight for architects or spatial planners as well as the founders and residents of ecovillages. The spatial and social structures can facilitate or hinder this aspect. A successful ecovillage is connected with the possibility for its residents to be able to switch between communality and individual space.

5.4. Meaning changes

The ecovillage and its residents are dynamic and move along with the circumstances. Along the way circumstances change, residents gain new insights, or their life course shifts. What seemed important at the beginning of a project does not have to be the same at the end. For example, Bram mentioned that the ecovillage has not become an utopia for him. There are aspects that he does find very pleasant, but at the same time he also sometimes has his frustrations. He says that for him it has not become a forever resting place by saying that he tries not to cling too rigidly onto how he had imagined it.

Suus shows how personal circumstances can change the meaning of the ecovillage. At the beginning of her search for another way of living she was mainly looking for connection with others. However, by meeting her current partner the meaning of the ecovillage has shifted. Nevertheless, it remains valuable for her to contribute to the initiative. It gives a lot of meaning to her life to contribute to a place that she supports from an idealistic point of view.

This shows that life in an ecovillage is a process in which ideals, reality, and personal meaning are continuously attuned to each other. It is not a fixed project but a dynamic environment in which residents must deal with change and find their own balance between personal circumstances and collective commitment.

5.5. Reflection on methodology

In this study, a biographical method was applied to allow the residents and founders to share the meanings they attribute to their ecovillage, as well as their motivations and experiences. This was achieved by giving the interviewees the space and trust to tell their own story. The aim was to stay close to the residents' and founders' experiences without projecting too many external ideas onto them.

Besides offering insight in the meaning, motivation, and experiences of the residents and founders, the method also gave insight in their development over time and the way this process unfolds. If a more direct research method had been employed, in which the interviews exclusively focused on predetermined themes, these developments over time would likely have been less visible. A method more focused on predetermined themes, would have offered a different perspective and yielded different insights. It could, for example, have investigated these themes in greater depth. Such an approach would, however, have been less suitable with the exploratory nature of this study.

Attention must be given to the fact that this study has an exploratory character and therefore a limited number of interviewees. The results therefore cannot simply be generalised to all ecovillages. However, it does show insight into the variation in motivations and meanings that founders and residents can have for their ecovillage. Future research could focus on scaling up the study to increase generalisability. In addition, it would be interesting to conduct longitudinal research to follow changes in meaning-making over time and/or to set up a comparative study that follows meaning-making in different phases of the ecovillage (initiation, scaling up, realisation, habitation).

6. Conclusion

6.1. Why ecovillage residents and founders choose to live in an ecovillage

In the results it emerges that the 'regular' living environment of the founders and residents interviewed in this research is insufficiently connected with their values, ideals, and needs. They indicated being dissatisfied with the planned and organised way of social life in the Netherlands or the way in which a sustainable life can be arranged. This led to frustrations among the residents and developers and made their 'regular' living place feel unsatisfying to them.

Although they had adopted and internalised common, standard expectations about how to live and how to interact with others, these norms no longer felt right to them. They no longer fit with their personal ideas about a good and meaningful life. This makes their experience stand in stark contrast with the dominant way in which social life in the Netherlands is generally shaped, as they illustrate with examples.

6.2. How the ecovillage lifestyle is experienced by their residents and founders

Overall, the ecovillage residents and founders interviewed for this research experienced the ecovillage as aligning better with their needs, ideals, and values. It seems that there is less of a contradiction between what they find valuable in life and their lifestyle. However, simultaneously certain aspects of living in an ecovillage can be experienced as challenging. Particularly the workload and limited physical and mental space are demanding for some. However, these aspects were expected by them beforehand and they did not let this hold them back.

6.3. The meaning the ecovillage residents and founders attribute to their ecovillage

Generally, the ecovillage offered a solution for the interviewees. It gave them the possibility to shape a lifestyle that aligns with their ideals of, among other things, connectedness and ecological responsibility. By stepping outside this system and creating alternative forms of dwelling, they found freedom and ways to live in a way that better supports their personal values and ideas about a good life.

Their choice for another lifestyle also exposes their conscious as well as unconscious critique of the dominant culture. It challenges the system of 'regular' living that offers little room for sustainable choices and social connectedness. The ecovillage can be seen as a pioneering

place, where the residents and founders find out how things could be done differently. In this way they discover for themselves different meanings of living that may resist the established norms. From a constructivist perspective this shows how their awareness of societal expectations shaped and challenged their ideas about what a good life entails.

6.4. Relevance of the research

This research suggests that in regular forms of dwelling limited room for action can be experienced to live according to their residents' social or ecological values. For policymakers and urban planners this means that possibly more space and support may be needed for the establishment of collective and sustainable housing initiatives. Next to that, ecovillages function as experimental spaces, they form niches where alternative practices can be tried out. This has societal value because such places can function as laboratories for sustainable and social innovations and could be scaled up or adopted in the future.

The impression this research gives, is that the ecovillage cannot be captured from a single perspective. It shows that ecovillages are multidimensional practices, in which social, ecological, and personal meanings are constructed simultaneously. For future research it may therefore be relevant to understand ecovillages as places where multiple dimensions of motivations, reasons, and meaning apply.

AI statement: during the execution of this thesis, the author used the AI tools ChatGPT and Microsoft Copilot (both GPT-5) for translational features, spelling check and fluency in text. The outputs generated by these tools are critically evaluated and only incorporated according with the author's own judgement and insights. The author takes full responsibility for the content presented in this thesis.

References

- Adams, P. (2006). Exploring social constructivism: Theories and practicalities. *Education 3-13*, 34(3), 243–257. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03004270600898893>
- Alberro, H. (2020). *Ecotopia Rising: An Ecocritical Analysis of Radical Environmental Activists as Ecotopian Expressions Amid Anthropocene Decline*.
- Avelino, F., & Kunze, I. (2009). Exploring the Transition Potential of the Ecovillage Movement. <http://www.community-research.eu>
- Barani, S., Alibeygi, A. H., & Papzan, A. (2018). A framework to identify and develop potential ecovillages: Meta-analysis from the studies of world's ecovillages. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 43, 275–289. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2018.08.036>
- Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek. (2024, 17 december). Prognose: huishoudensgroei in de toekomst vooral door meer alleenstaanden. Centraal Bureau Voor de Statistiek. Retrieved on 8-12-2025 from <https://www.cbs.nl/nl-nl/nieuws/2024/51/prognose-huishoudensgroei-in-de-toekomst-vooral-door-meer-alleenstaanden>
- Daly, M. (2017). Quantifying the environmental impact of ecovillages and co-housing communities: a systematic literature review. In *Local Environment* (Vol. 22, Issue 11, pp. 1358–1377). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2017.1348342>
- De Boer, C. (July 12, 2023). Een ecodorp in Weert: voor natuurliefhebbers en mensen die even een pauze in hun leven nodig hebben. [de limburger.nl](https://www.limburger.nl).
- Demey, D., Berrington, A., Evandrou, M., & Falkingham, J. (2013). Pathways into living alone in mid-life: Diversity and policy implications. *Advances in Life Course Research*, 18(3), 161–174. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.alcr.2013.02.001>
- Dias, M. A., Loureiro, C. F. B., Chevitarrese, L., & Souza, C. D. M. E. (2017). The meaning and relevance of ecovillages for the construction of sustainable societal alternatives. *Ambiente e Sociedade*, 20(3), 79–96. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1809-4422ASOC0083V2032017>
- Ecodorp Boekel (July 30, 2020). Ad Vlems has a dream [Video]. YouTube. Accessed on 12-12-2023, from https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=A_Q73oUqHm8

Findhorn Foundation (n.d.), The story of the Findhorn Foundation. Accessed on 12-12-2023, from <https://www.findhorn.org/about-us/findhorn-foundation-our-story/>

Global Ecovillage Network Nederland (2021). Jaarverslag 2021 GEN-Nederland

Global Ecovillage Network Nederland (2022). Jaarverslag 2022 GEN-Nederland

Global Ecovillage Network Nederland (2023). Jaarverslag 2023 GEN-Nederland

Guest, A. M., & Wierzbicki, S. K. (1999). Social Ties at the Neighborhood Level: Two Decades of GSS Evidence: Two Decades of GSS Evidence. *Urban Affairs Review*, 35(1), 92-111. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10780879922184301>

Haxeltine, A.; Avelino, F., Pel, B., Dumitru, A.; Kemp, R.; Longhurst, N. Chilvers, J. and Wittmayer, J. M. (2016). A framework for Transformative Social Innovation (TRANSIT Working Paper # 5), TRANSIT: EU SSH.2013.3.2-1 Grant agreement no: 613169.

Hein, G. E. (1999). Is Meaning Making Constructivism? Is Constructivism Meaning Making? *The Exhibitionist*, Vol. 18, No. 2, p. 15-18

Heinonen, A. (2023). Alone and together in domestic space: navigating spatial and conceptual relationship boundaries in Finnish small-scale communes. *Families Relationships And Societies*, 13(4), 495–511. <https://doi.org/10.1332/20467435y2023d000000005>

Hoogerbrugge, M. M., & Burger, M. J. (2018). Neighborhood-Based social capital and life satisfaction: the case of Rotterdam, The Netherlands. *Urban Geography*, 39(10), 1484–1509. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02723638.2018.1474609>

Illeris, K. (2009). Contemporary Theories of Learning: Learning Theorists . . . In Their Own Words. Routledge.

Jafari Amineh, R., & Davatgari Asl, H. (2015). Journal of Social Sciences, Literature and Languages Review of Constructivism and Social Constructivism. In ©2015 JSSLL Journal (Vol. 1, Issue 1).

Joubert, K. (April 27, 2017). What is an Ecovillage? Reflections from the Network. Global Ecovillage Network International. Retrieved on 13-5-2024 from <https://ecovillage.org/what-is-an-ecovillage/>

Juskaite, G. (2019). Strategies of De-growth: The Role of Eco-communities in Politics of Change. <https://www.nmbu.no/fakultet/landsam/institutt/noragric>

Kersten, P., Mund, M., & Neyer, F. J. (2023). Does living alone mean being alone? Personal networks of solo-living adults in midlife. *International Journal Of Behavioral Development*, 48(1), 12–24. <https://doi.org/10.1177/01650254231206329>

KNAW; NFU; NWO; TO2-federatie; Vereniging Hogescholen; VSNU (2018): Nederlandse gedragscode wetenschappelijke integriteit. DANS. <https://doi.org/10.17026/dans-2cj-nvww>

Kunze, I., Avelino, F. (2015): Social Innovation and the Global Ecovillage Network. Research Report, TRANSIT: EU SSH.2013.3.2-1 Grant agreement no: 613169

Kvale, S. (2007). *Doing interviews*. SAGE publications Ltd. ISBN 978-0-7619-4977-0

Lachman, M. E., Teshale, S., & Agrigoroaei, S. (2014). Midlife as a pivotal period in the life course. *International Journal Of Behavioral Development*, 39(1), 20–31.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0165025414533223>

Looden, M. (June 25, 2023). Pim woont in het eerste huisje van het ecodorp in Ter Apel. 'Ik wil hier nog graag lang blijven'. *Dagblad van het Noorden.nl*.

Loorbach, D., Oxenaar, S., & Dutch Research Institute for Transitions (DRIFT). (2018). *Counting on Nature: Transitions to a natural capital positive economy*. In Report Commissioned By The Dutch Ministry Of Agriculture, Nature, And Food Quality.

Martin, L., White, M. P., Hunt, A., Richardson, M., Pahl, S., & Burt, J. (2020b). Nature contact, nature connectedness and associations with health, wellbeing and pro-environmental behaviours. *Journal Of Environmental Psychology*, 68, 101389.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2020.101389>

Mascini, L. (January 28, 2024). Toekomstige bewoners bouwen zelf een ecodorp in Wormerveer: 'We hebben gekeken of we konden leven zonder rioolaansluiting maar dat blijkt niet heel veel schoner'. *Noordhollands Dagblad.nl*.

Mollenhorst, G. (2015b). Neighbour Relations in the Netherlands: New Developments. *Tijdschrift Voor Economische en Sociale Geografie*, 106(1), 110–119.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/tesg.12138>

Ongena, Y. (2005). *Interviewer and Respondent Interaction in Survey Interviews (1st ed.)*. Vrije Universiteit, Amsterdam.

Putnam, R. D. (2000). *Bowling alone: the collapse and revival of American community*. Simon & Schuster.

Ruijters, M. & Simons, R. J. (2012). *De canon van het leren: 50 concepten en hun grondleggers*. Vakmedianet.

Ruijters, M. (2006). *Liefde voor leren: over diversiteit van leren en ontwikkelen in en van organisaties*. Kluwer.

Schönbach, D. M. I., Tiscareno-Osorno, X., MacIntyre, T. E., Smith, S., MacIntyre, D., & Demetriou, Y. (2022b). What socio-demographic characteristics of university students in Southern Germany predict their urban nature connectedness? *PLoS ONE*, 17(8), e0272344. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0272344>

Sheffield, D., Butler, C. W., & Richardson, M. (2022b). Improving Nature Connectedness in Adults: A Meta-Analysis, Review and Agenda. *Sustainability*, 14(19), 12494. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141912494>

Sobotka, T., & Berghammer, C. (2021b). Demography of family change in Europe. In Edward Elgar Publishing eBooks. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781788975544.00019>

Taylor, S. & Littleton K. (2006). Biographies in talk: A narrative-discursive research approach. *Qualitative Sociological review* Volume 2 issue 1

Ten Hoedt, M., van Barneveld, J. (April 14, 2014). Zoektocht naar een rafelrand. *De Gelderlander*.

Törnqvist, M. (2020b). Communal Intimacy: Formalization, Egalitarianism, and Exchangeability in Collective Housing. *Social Forces*, 100(1), 273–292. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sf/soaa094>

Victor, C., Scambler, S., Bond, J., & Bowling, A. (2000b). Being alone in later life: loneliness, social isolation and living alone. *Reviews in Clinical Gerontology*, 10(4), 407–417. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0959259800104101>

Volker, B., Flap, H., & Lindenberg, S. (2006). When are neighbourhoods communities? community in Dutch neighbourhoods. *European Sociological Review*, 23(1), 99–114. <https://doi.org/10.1093/esr/jcl022>

Yanow, D. (1999). *Conducting interpretive policy analysis*. SAGE Publications, Inc. ISBN 9780761908272

ANNEX I

Toestemmingsformulier

Onderzoek Enquête/Interview Evenement Nieuwsbrief Hergebruik Andere:
[naam]

Door uw toestemming te geven, verklaart u dat u deze persoonsgegevens vrijwillig hebt verstrekt. De door u verstrekte persoonsgegevens worden alleen gebruikt voor het doel waarvoor u deze heeft verstrekt. U heeft het recht op inzage, verwijdering, correctie of beperking van de verwerking van persoonsgegevens, alsmede het recht op bezwaar en het recht op gegevensoverdraagbaarheid. Meer hierover op [Integriteit & Privacy - WUR](#)

Informatie over de verwerking van persoonsgegevens: [Reglement bescherming persoonsgegevens - WUR](#)

In geval van een geschil kunt u een klacht indienen bij privacy@wur.nl of bij de Autoriteit Persoonsgegevens via www.autoriteitpersoonsgegevens.nl

Projectnaam: Masterthesis ecodorpen

Looptijd: 1 november. 2023 – 1 oktober 2024

Paper Verslag Promotie Nationaal onderzoek Internationaal onderzoek WOT-taken Overig: (naam)

Korte projectomschrijving

Dit onderzoek betreft een afstudeeronderzoek van een masterstudent voor de master Bos- en Natuurbeheer aan de Wageningen Universiteit, bij Wageningen Environmental Research (WENR) binnen het project Biotraces. Het afstudeeronderzoek gaat over de betekenis van ecodorpen voor hun bewoners. Dit wordt onderzocht vanuit het idee dat er verschillende beweegredenen zijn voor de ecodorp-bewoners om een ecodorp op te zetten en er te wonen. In Nederland is het niet gemakkelijk een ecodorp op te zetten, dus waar zij toch doorzetten en dit wel doen worden sterke beweegredenen en motivaties verwacht. Deze motivaties en beweegredenen worden vervolgens bekeken door de lens van welke betekenis het ecodorp heeft voor ecodorp-oprichters en -bewoners.

Deze persoonsgegevens worden van u verzameld

Opname van gesprekken en, als u daar toestemming voor geeft, fotomateriaal.

Geluidsopname van gesprekken zullen worden geanalyseerd om de betekenis die ecodorpen hebben voor ecodorp- bewoners in kaart te brengen. Informatie uit de gesprekken wordt niet persoonlijk herleidbaar verwerkt. Dat wil zeggen dat voor de rapportage alle persoonsgegevens worden geanonimiseerd.

Hoe worden uw persoonsgegevens opgeslagen en beveiligd

De opnames, foto's en ruwe data worden opgeslagen op een projectshare waar alleen onderzoekers van het WUR-onderzoeksteam toegang tot hebben. Deze onderzoekers zijn werkzaam bij Wageningen Environmental Research (WENR). Gegevens worden bewaard in overeenstemming met de algemene richtlijnen van de Wageningen University & Research

[Informatiebeveiliging - WUR](#)

Hoe lang worden uw persoonsgegevens bewaard.

Ruwe data (met persoonsgegevens) wordt in de projectshare van het onderzoeksteam bewaard en zal 5 jaar na het einde van het project (2026) worden verwijderd.

Geanonimiseerde en geanalyseerde gegevens van het onderzoek worden in een open access database opgeslagen voor tenminste 20 jaar.

De genoemde of een deel van de persoonsgegevens worden gedeeld met

Geanonimiseerde en geanalyseerde gegevens worden gedeeld met organisatie binnen de EU die deel uitmaken van het BIOTraCeS consortium.

Dit zijn:

- Goeteborgs Universitet (UGOT), Zweden
- Centro de Estudio Socias (CES), Portugal
- Okologiai Kutatokozpont (CER), Hongarije
- Asociacion BC3, Basque Centre for Climate Resilience (BC3)
- Mykolo Romerio Universitetas (MRU), Litouwen
- Universita Degli Studi di Catania (UNICT), Italië
- Universteit Twente (UT), Nederland
- Universitatea Babes Bolyai (UBB), Roemenië
- European Science Communication Institute (ESCI), Duitsland
- Centro de Estudios Ambientales (CEA), Spanje

Contactgegevens masterstudent en afstudeerbegeleider

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Roel During, roel.during@wur.nl, +31317419000 (Afstudeerbegeleider)

Naam deelnemer aan het onderzoek:

Ik bevestig hierbij mijn toestemming voor gespreksopname en het gebruik van mijn persoonsgegevens zoals hierboven beschreven.

Ik in de toekomst updates over dit project of evenementen wil ontvangen.

Datum en handtekening

ANNEX II

Interview topics

The topics the interview will explore have been made specific to ensure the main and sub-research questions are effectively addressed in the interviews:

- **To what characteristics of ecovillages/the ecovillage lifestyle feel the ecovillage residents attracted to**
 - What philosophy or lifestyle do they connect with ecovillages
 - Why do they feel connected to this philosophy or lifestyle

- **How life changes before and after joining an ecovillage community**
 - How did their life look like before joining the ecovillage and after.
 - How do the ecovillage residents perceive this change of environment

- **How personal experiences and events influence motivations to join**
 - How does their background influence their beliefs and values, which connect to the ecovillage (lifestyle)
 - Are there certain life events that influenced their interest in ecovillages

- **How the ecovillage residents' visions on society evolve in social interactions**
 - Does living in the ecovillage shape or change their views on societal issues
 - What kind of communication is there within the ecovillage and how does the interaction with the 'outside world' look like